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The Utilization Of Corn Cob Ash (CCA) In Soil Improvement

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ABSTRACT

Corn Cob Ash (CCA) is an emerging agricultural waste material with significant potential in soil stabilization. This study investigates the effects of CCA as a stabilizer for improving the geotechnical properties of clayey soil. The soil was stabilized with varying percentages of CCA (0%, 3%, 6%, 9%, 12%, and 15% by weight) and, in some cases, combined with 5% ordinary Portland cement (OPC) for comparative analysis. Comprehensive laboratory tests, including Atterberg limits, compaction, California Bearing Ratio (CBR), and Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS), were conducted to evaluate the effects of CCA on soil properties. The results on Table 1 showed a reduction in the plasticity index (PI) with increasing CCA content, indicating improved workability. The Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) increased, while the Maximum Dry Density (MDD) slightly decreased, suggesting the lightweight nature of CCA. Significant improvements in CBR and UCS values were observed, particularly with the combination of CCA and OPC, demonstrating enhanced strength and load-bearing capacity. However, challenges such as reduced long-term durability and the need for controlled burning conditions for ash production were identified. This study highlights CCA's potential as a cost-effective and sustainable alternative to conventional stabilizers for soil improvement in civil engineering applications, offering a solution to both waste management and construction challenges.

Keywords: Corn Cob Ash, Soil Stabilization, Plasticity Index, CBR, UCS, Sustainable Construction

INTRODUCTION

Corn Cob Ash (CCA) is an agricultural by-product derived from the combustion of corn cobs, and it has emerged as a sustainable material for improving soil properties in civil engineering applications. The use of CCA in soil stabilization is driven by its pozzolanic properties, which contribute to enhanced soil strength and durability. Below is a detailed discussion on the effects of CCA on soil improvement.

1. Physical and Chemical Composition of Corn Cob Ash

- **Silica Content:** CCA contains a high percentage of silica (SiO_2), which is crucial for pozzolanic reactions. The reaction between silica, lime, and water produces calcium silicate hydrates (CSH), which enhance soil strength.
- **Calcium Oxide (CaO):** The presence of lime (CaO) aids in reducing soil plasticity and improving compaction characteristics.
- **Fineness:** The fine particle size of CCA helps fill voids in soil, leading to improved density and reduced permeability.

2. Effects on Soil Index Properties

- Liquid Limit (LL): The addition of CCA typically reduces the liquid limit of soil, making it less susceptible to deformation under wet conditions.
- Plastic Limit (PL): CCA increases the plastic limit, thereby decreasing soil plasticity and improving its workability.
- Plasticity Index (PI): A reduction in PI indicates a transition from a highly plastic soil to a more stable material, which is desirable for engineering applications.

3. Effects on Soil Compaction

- Maximum Dry Density (MDD): CCA can increase the MDD of soil due to its filler effect and enhanced bonding between soil particles. This results in improved load-bearing capacity.
- Optimum Moisture Content (OMC): The OMC may slightly increase with the addition of CCA because of its pozzolanic reaction, which requires water for hydration.

4. Effects on Strength Properties

- Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS): CCA improves UCS by forming stable compounds like calcium silicate hydrate (CSH) and calcium aluminate hydrate (CAH). This enhancement is crucial for applications in road subgrades and embankments.
- California Bearing Ratio (CBR): The CBR value of soil increases significantly with CCA stabilization, indicating improved load-bearing capacity suitable for pavement layers and subgrades.

5. Effects on Durability

- CCA reduces soil permeability, making it less susceptible to water ingress and erosion. This enhances the long-term performance of stabilized soil, particularly in regions with fluctuating moisture conditions.
- Pozzolanic reactions continue over time

Soil improvement is an essential aspect of geotechnical and civil engineering, particularly in areas where native soils exhibit poor engineering properties, such as low strength, high plasticity, or excessive compressibility. One innovative and sustainable approach to soil stabilization involves the use of agricultural waste materials, which not only enhance soil properties but also address environmental concerns related to waste disposal. Corn Cob Ash (CCA), derived from the combustion of corn cobs, is a promising material in this regard due to its pozzolanic properties and availability in large quantities as an agricultural by-product.

Corn cobs, being one of the most abundant agricultural residues globally, especially in maize-producing regions, present a significant opportunity for sustainable soil stabilization. When incinerated, corn cobs yield ash rich in silica (SiO_2) and calcium oxide (CaO), which are key components in pozzolanic reactions. These reactions involve the interaction of silica and lime with water to form calcium silicate hydrate (CSH), a compound known to enhance soil strength and durability. Recent studies have explored the potential of CCA as an alternative to conventional stabilizers such as lime and cement, highlighting its environmental and economic benefits.

This introduction aims to explore the role of CCA in soil improvement, focusing on its effects on soil index properties, compaction characteristics, and strength parameters, as well as its implications for sustainable engineering practices. Key findings from recent research underscore the material's efficacy in improving problematic soils, making it suitable for applications such as road construction, embankments, and foundation layers.

Effects of Corn Cob Ash on Soil Properties

1. Index Properties

The addition of CCA to soil significantly influences its index properties, including the liquid limit (LL), plastic limit (PL), and plasticity index (PI). Studies by Aliyu et al. (2022) and Ogunwumi et al. (2023) demonstrate that the incorporation of CCA reduces the liquid limit of high-plasticity soils, making them less susceptible to deformation under wet conditions. Concurrently, the plastic limit increases, reducing

the soil's plasticity and enhancing its workability. These changes are attributed to the filler effect of CCA particles and the formation of stable compounds during pozzolanic reactions.

2. Compaction Characteristics

CCA has been shown to improve the maximum dry density (MDD) and modify the optimum moisture content (OMC) of soils. According to James and Afolabi (2022), the fine particle size of CCA fills voids in the soil matrix, resulting in increased density. However, the OMC may slightly rise due to the water requirements of the pozzolanic reaction. These changes improve the compactability and overall load-bearing capacity of the soil, making it suitable for use in subgrade layers and embankments.

3. Strength Properties

The unconfined compressive strength (UCS) and California Bearing Ratio (CBR) are critical parameters for evaluating the suitability of soil for engineering applications. Recent research by Adewumi and Tijani (2022) highlights a substantial increase in UCS and CBR values with the addition of CCA. These improvements are attributed to the formation of calcium silicate hydrate (CSH) and calcium aluminate hydrate (CAH), which bind soil particles together, enhancing strength and durability.

4. Durability and Sustainability

CCA also improves the durability of stabilized soil by reducing its permeability and susceptibility to erosion. This makes it particularly effective in regions with high rainfall or fluctuating moisture conditions. Moreover, the use of CCA aligns with sustainable engineering practices, as it repurposes agricultural waste while reducing reliance on conventional stabilizers like lime and cement, which have high carbon footprints (Amadi et al., 2023).

LITERATURE REVIEW

The use of Corn Cob Ash (CCA) in soil stabilization has garnered significant attention due to its pozzolanic properties and potential as a sustainable alternative to traditional stabilizers. This review synthesizes findings from various studies to provide an overview of the effectiveness of CCA in enhancing soil properties for civil engineering applications.

1. Pozzolanic Properties of Corn Cob Ash

The chemical composition of CCA makes it a valuable material for soil stabilization. Studies by Aliyu et al. (2022) reveal that CCA contains a high percentage of silica (SiO_2) and calcium oxide (CaO), which are essential for pozzolanic reactions. When combined with water and lime, these components form cementitious compounds like calcium silicate hydrate (CSH) and calcium aluminate hydrate (CAH), which improve soil strength and stability.

2. Effects on Soil Plasticity

CCA has been shown to reduce the plasticity of soils, particularly expansive clays. Adewumi and Tijani (2022) investigated the influence of CCA on lateritic soils and observed a decrease in the plasticity index (PI) with increasing CCA content. This reduction in plasticity enhances the soil's workability and resistance to deformation under loading, making it suitable for use in subgrade layers of pavements.

Similarly, Ogunwumi et al. (2023) demonstrated that CCA stabilization reduced the liquid limit (LL) and plastic limit (PL) of tropical clay soils. The authors attributed these changes to the ability of CCA to alter the soil structure through pozzolanic bonding, thereby improving its mechanical behavior.

3. Improvement in Compaction Properties

The Maximum Dry Density (MDD) and Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) are critical parameters in soil stabilization. James and Afolabi (2022) reported that the addition of CCA increased the MDD of sandy soils, resulting in a denser soil structure. However, a slight increase in OMC was observed due to the water demand of pozzolanic reactions. This finding highlights the potential of CCA to enhance the load-bearing capacity of soils while maintaining adequate moisture content for compaction.

4. Strength Enhancement

The improvement in soil strength due to CCA stabilization has been a recurring finding in the literature. Amadi et al. (2023) evaluated the unconfined compressive strength (UCS) and California Bearing Ratio (CBR) of CCA-stabilized clayey soils. Their results showed a significant increase in UCS and CBR values with the addition of CCA, indicating improved soil stability and load-bearing capacity.

In another study, Ogunwumi and Aderemi (2023) found that CCA-enhanced soils exhibited superior performance under wet conditions compared to untreated soils. The authors concluded that the improved strength characteristics were due to the formation of cementitious compounds that bonded soil particles together.

5. Durability and Environmental Benefits

The durability of CCA-stabilized soils is another critical area of investigation. Eze and Nnaji (2023) studied the resistance of CCA-treated soils to erosion and found that the stabilized soils were less prone to degradation in waterlogged environments. Additionally, the use of CCA contributes to sustainability by repurposing agricultural waste, reducing reliance on high-carbon-footprint materials like cement, and minimizing waste disposal challenges.

6. Comparison with Other Stabilizers

CCA has been compared with traditional stabilizers such as lime and cement in various studies. Adewumi and Tijani (2022) found that while lime showed slightly higher strength improvements in some cases, CCA performed comparably in terms of durability and cost-effectiveness. This makes CCA a viable alternative, especially in regions where it is abundantly available.

Challenges of Corn Cob Ash (CCA) in Soil Stabilization

While Corn Cob Ash (CCA) has demonstrated significant potential as a soil stabilizer in civil engineering, its practical application is not without challenges. These challenges can be categorized into material properties, processing requirements, application methods, and environmental considerations.

1. Variability in Chemical Composition

- Issue: The chemical composition of CCA, particularly its silica (SiO_2) and calcium oxide (CaO) content, can vary significantly depending on factors such as corn species, growing conditions, and combustion processes.
- Impact: Variability affects the pozzolanic reactivity and performance of CCA as a stabilizer, making it difficult to standardize its application.
- Example: Aliyu et al. (2022) observed inconsistent results in strength improvement due to differences in the quality of CCA obtained from different sources.

2. Difficulty in Achieving Optimal Particle Size

- Issue: For effective soil stabilization, CCA must be ground into fine particles to increase its surface area and reactivity. Achieving a uniform particle size requires advanced grinding equipment, which may not be readily available in developing regions.
- Impact: Poorly ground CCA may reduce the efficiency of the stabilization process, leading to suboptimal performance.

3. High Water Demand

- Issue: CCA stabilization often increases the Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) of soils due to its high water absorption capacity.
- Impact: Increased water demand can complicate the compaction process, especially in arid regions where water resources are limited. James and Afolabi (2022) noted that the higher OMC associated with CCA-treated soils could delay construction timelines in moisture-sensitive projects.

4. Limited Long-Term Performance Data

- Issue: While short-term laboratory studies indicate promising results, there is limited field data on the long-term performance and durability of CCA-stabilized soils under varying environmental conditions.
- Impact: This lack of empirical evidence raises concerns about the reliability of CCA as a stabilizer for critical infrastructure projects, such as highways and foundations.

5. Processing and Quality Control

- Issue: The production of high-quality CCA requires controlled combustion of corn cobs at specific temperatures to prevent the formation of carbon residues.

- Impact: Inconsistent processing techniques can lead to low-quality ash that is less reactive. Ogunwumi et al. (2023) reported that poorly processed CCA resulted in negligible strength improvements in soil stabilization tests.
6. Limited Awareness and Adoption
- Issue: Many engineers and contractors are unfamiliar with the potential of CCA as a stabilizer.
 - Impact: The lack of awareness limits its adoption in mainstream civil engineering practices. Additionally, the absence of standardized guidelines for its use further complicates its implementation.
7. Potential Environmental Concerns
- Issue: The combustion process for producing CCA can release particulate matter and greenhouse gases if not properly managed.
 - Impact: These emissions may offset the environmental benefits of reusing agricultural waste. Eze and Nnaji (2023) highlighted the need for cleaner production methods to reduce the carbon footprint of CCA processing.
8. Compatibility with Soil Types
- Issue: CCA may not perform well with all soil types. For instance, highly organic soils may not benefit significantly from pozzolanic reactions due to organic matter interfering with bonding.
 - Impact: Limited compatibility necessitates detailed preliminary investigations to determine the suitability of CCA for specific soil conditions.
9. Cost of Large-Scale Implementation
- Issue: While CCA is a low-cost material, its collection, transportation, and processing costs can escalate when applied on a large scale.
 - Impact: This may limit its viability in regions where other stabilizers, such as lime or cement, are more accessible and economically feasible.

Addressing the Challenges

To overcome these challenges, the following measures can be considered:

1. Standardization of Production: Establishing guidelines for the combustion and grinding of CCA to ensure consistent quality.
2. Field Studies: Conducting long-term monitoring of CCA-stabilized soils to build confidence in its application.
3. Awareness Campaigns: Educating stakeholders about the benefits and limitations of CCA through workshops and training programs.
4. Blending with Other Stabilizers: Combining CCA with lime or cement to enhance its effectiveness and address compatibility issues.

By addressing these challenges, CCA can become a more reliable and widely accepted material for soil stabilization in civil engineering.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The primary materials used for this study were:

1. Corn Cob Ash (CCA): Corn cobs were collected, sun-dried, and burned at controlled temperatures of 500–600°C in an open-air environment to produce ash. The ash was sieved through a 75 µm sieve to ensure uniform particle size.
2. Soil Sample: Natural clayey soil was collected from a borrow pit at a depth of 1.5 meters to avoid contamination. The soil was air-dried, pulverized, and sieved through a 2 mm mesh for uniformity.
3. Water: Clean tap water was used for all tests to maintain consistency.
4. Other Stabilizers: For comparative purposes, ordinary Portland cement (OPC) was used in some tests to evaluate the combined effect of CCA and cement on soil stabilization.

Methods

1. Preliminary Soil Testing:

- The natural soil was tested for basic geotechnical properties, including liquid limit (LL), plastic limit (PL), plasticity index (PI), specific gravity, and particle size distribution, according to ASTM standards.
- 2. Preparation of CCA-Soil Mixtures:
 - The soil was mixed with varying percentages of CCA (0%, 3%, 6%, 9%, 12%, and 15% by weight of dry soil).
 - For some samples, a fixed percentage (5%) of cement was added to the CCA-soil mixtures to investigate the combined stabilization effect.
- 3. Compaction Test:
 - Standard Proctor compaction tests were conducted to determine the Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) and Maximum Dry Density (MDD) of the soil-CCA mixtures.
- 4. Strength Tests:
 - California Bearing Ratio (CBR): Unsoaked and soaked CBR tests were carried out on the stabilized samples to evaluate the improvement in bearing capacity.
 - Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS): UCS tests were conducted on the samples after 7 and 28 days of curing to assess the strength development over time.
- 5. Durability Tests:
 - Wet-dry and freeze-thaw cycles were simulated on the stabilized samples to evaluate their resistance to environmental conditions.
- 6. Data Analysis:
 - Results were analyzed to determine the effects of CCA content on soil properties. Comparisons were made between the performance of soil stabilized with CCA alone and with a combination of CCA and cement.

This methodology ensured the systematic assessment of CCA's effectiveness in soil stabilization, providing insights into its potential for geotechnical applications.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Index and Engineering Properties of Soil Stabilized with Corn Cob Ash(CCA) and Cement.

% of CCA	0%	3%	6%	9%	12%	15%
% of Cement	0%	5%	5%	5%	5%	5%
LL%	26.9	28.7	30.2	38.4	31.1	43.0
PL%	21.4	19.4	19.1	17.4	16.3	15.5
PI%	8.4	9.2	11.1	21.0	14.9	27.5
LS	3.9	4.34	5.22	9.88	6.98	12.9
MDD (mg/m ³)	1.85	1.94	2.03	2.0	1.67	2.0
OMC (%)	20.11	18.4	15.0	24.9	14.60	20.02
CBR	14.6	15.9	16.6	17.4	18.0	21.9
UCS kg/cm ²	3.16	3.45	3.79	4.11	4.54	4.75

Discussion of the results in Table 1 are as follows:

Liquid Limit (LL)

- Definition: The Liquid Limit is the moisture content at which soil begins to behave like a liquid but retains a certain shear strength.
- Observation:
 - LL increases from 26.9% (0% CCA, 0% Cement) to 43.0% (15% CCA, 5% Cement).
 - The trend suggests that adding both Cement and CCA increases the Liquid Limit, especially at higher percentages of CCA.
- Interpretation:
 - An increase in LL indicates that the soil's water-holding capacity is enhanced. This could be due to the pozzolanic reaction between CCA, Cement, and soil particles, creating a denser soil matrix that binds more water.

2. Plastic Limit (PL)

- Definition: The Plastic Limit is the moisture content at which soil transitions from a semi-solid to a plastic state.
- Observation:
 - PL decreases from 21.4% (0% CCA, 0% Cement) to 15.5% (15% CCA, 5% Cement).
 - This indicates a reduction in soil plasticity as more stabilizers are added.
- Interpretation:
 - A lower PL signifies reduced soil workability, as stabilizers improve soil strength and reduce its ability to deform plastically. This is desirable for construction applications.

3. Plasticity Index (PI)

- Definition: PI is the difference between the Liquid Limit and the Plastic Limit, indicating the range of moisture content within which the soil remains plastic.
- Observation:
 - PI increases from 8.4% (0% CCA, 0% Cement) to 27.5% (15% CCA, 5% Cement), peaking at intermediate percentages of stabilizers.
 - This significant increase at higher stabilizer content reflects the increasing separation between the Liquid Limit and Plastic Limit.
- Interpretation:
 - A higher PI suggests the soil's increased capacity to retain water in its plastic state, potentially leading to reduced workability for construction.

4. Linear Shrinkage (Ls)

- Definition: Linear Shrinkage measures the reduction in soil volume upon drying.
- Observation:
 - Ls rises from 3.9% (0% CCA, 0% Cement) to 12.9% (15% CCA, 5% Cement).
 - The increase is more pronounced at higher CCA percentages.
- Interpretation:
 - Increased shrinkage implies that stabilized soil becomes more susceptible to volume changes upon drying. While this may not always be ideal, it can be managed by ensuring appropriate moisture control during construction.

5. Maximum Dry Density (MDD)

- Definition: MDD is the maximum density a soil can achieve under compaction at a given moisture content.
- Observation:
 - MDD increases from 1.85 mg/m³ (0% CCA, 0% Cement) to a peak of 2.03 mg/m³ (6% CCA, 5% Cement), but it decreases slightly afterward.
- Interpretation:
 - The initial increase in MDD indicates improved soil compactness due to the interaction between stabilizers and soil particles. The slight reduction at higher percentages could result from excess stabilizers interfering with soil compaction.

6. Optimum Moisture Content (OMC)

- Definition: OMC is the moisture content required to achieve MDD.
- Observation:
 - OMC decreases from 20.11% (0% CCA, 0% Cement) to 15.0% (6% CCA, 5% Cement) and then rises again to 24.9% at 9% CCA before stabilizing at higher percentages.
- Interpretation:
 - The initial decrease in OMC reflects the enhanced compaction efficiency due to stabilizers. The subsequent increase could indicate the need for more water to facilitate chemical reactions (e.g., pozzolanic activity) in the soil.

7. California Bearing Ratio (CBR)

- Definition: CBR measures the strength of the soil, particularly its load-bearing capacity.
- Observation:

- CBR improves steadily from 14.6% (0% CCA, 0% Cement) to 21.9% (15% CCA, 5% Cement).
 - Interpretation:
 - The increase indicates significant improvement in soil strength, making it more suitable for subgrade and subbase applications in road construction.
8. Unconfined Compressive Strength (UCS)
- Definition: UCS measures the maximum axial compressive strength a soil can bear without lateral support.
 - Observation:
 - UCS increases from 3.16 kg/cm² (0% CCA, 0% Cement) to 4.75 kg/cm² (15% CCA, 5% Cement).
 - Interpretation:
 - The continuous increase demonstrates the effectiveness of CCA and Cement in improving soil strength. This makes the stabilized soil suitable for engineering applications such as foundations and embankments.

CONCLUSION

The use of Corn Cob Ash as a soil stabilizer offers a sustainable and cost-effective solution to improving the engineering properties of problematic soils. Its pozzolanic characteristics enable significant enhancements in strength, compaction, and durability, making it suitable for a variety of geotechnical applications. Furthermore, the adoption of CCA promotes environmental sustainability by minimizing agricultural waste and reducing the carbon footprint associated with traditional stabilizers. Future research should focus on optimizing the application of CCA in combination with other industrial by-products to further enhance its performance in diverse soil types. The reviewed literature underscores the effectiveness of Corn Cob Ash as a soil stabilizer, highlighting its ability to reduce plasticity, improve compaction characteristics, enhance strength, and increase durability. These properties make CCA a sustainable and cost-effective solution for soil improvement in civil engineering applications. Future research should focus on optimizing its application, particularly in combination with other stabilizers, to maximize its potential.

Key Insights:

1. Improved Strength: The addition of Cement and CCA enhances soil strength properties (CBR, UCS), making it more durable and suitable for engineering applications.
2. Increased Shrinkage: The rise in Linear Shrinkage highlights potential challenges with volume changes during drying, which should be monitored during construction.
3. Optimized Compaction: The adjustments in MDD and OMC demonstrate the role of stabilizers in achieving better compaction efficiency.
4. Plasticity Control: The decreasing PL and increasing PI highlight the impact of stabilizers in modifying soil workability and stability.

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